

TRANSIENT HEAT CONDUCTION AND THERMAL STRESSES IN FUNCTIONALLY GRADED MATERIALS

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SUMMARY: A semi-analytical method is introduced to derive the transient thermal stress field in functionally graded materials (FGMs) where the physical properties vary continuously from one end of the material to the other end. The transient heat conduction problem in an FGM is solved first and the resulting temperature field is used to compute the thermal stresses in the FGM. The transient temperature field in the FGM is expressed by a series of eigenfunctions for the corresponding eigenvalue problem and the coefficients of each eigenfunction are determined by the Galerkin method with the extensive use of a computer algebra system. The physical fields in FGMs can be expressed semi-analytically while retaining all the relevant parameters. In addition, any change in boundary conditions such as temperature can be readily reflected without incurring the entire recalculation.

KEYWORDS: Functionally graded materials, micromechanics, Green's function, transient heat transfer, design.

INTRODUCTION

Functionally gradient materials (FGMs) distribute the material functions throughout the material body to achieve the maximum heat resistance and mechanical properties ([1] for example) for structures where one side is exposed extremely high temperature and the other side is exposed to extremely low temperature. Typically, ceramics can be used on one side exposed to high temperature while metals can be used on the other side where mechanical strength is in demand. Continuous mixtures of ceramics and metals are distributed in the intermediate range thus eliminating distinct phase interface that often causes cracks due to different thermal expansion at the interface. Because of the continuously varying material properties, analysis of FGM is complicated and many analytical methods developed for composites with distinct phases may not be directly applicable to FGMs.

In this paper, a micromechanical approach is used to obtain the thermoelastic fields in FGMs semi-analytically by the eigenfunction expansion method. The transient temperature fields in an FGM is expressed by eigenfunctions defined for the associated eigenvalue problem and the coefficient of each eigenfunction can be determined by the Galerkin method. This results in an algebraic eigenvalue problem which can be numerically solved by the Galerkin method using the permissible functions (polynomials or transcendental functions that match the boundary condition of FGMs). The thermal stress field is then expressed using the result from the transient thermal analysis, thus both the mechanical and thermal fields in FGMs can be expressed semi-analytically while retaining all the relevant parameters. This approach is suitable for optimum design of FGMs because of the reserved parameters representing the characteristics of FGMs. Although this method has been well-known, the implementation of the method for multi-dimensional and heterogeneous bodies is the first attempt to the author's best knowledge [2]. As an example, thermal stress distribution in a 2-D rectangular elastic body under transient heat conduction subject to the first kind displacement boundary condition is shown for demonstration. As the obtained expressions retain all the relevant parameters, the procedure is suited for sensitivity analysis.

TRANSIENT HEAT CONDUCTION

The energy equation for a general heterogeneous material is expressed as

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (K(\mathbf{r}) \nabla T(\mathbf{r})), \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the mass density, C_p is the specific heat, $T(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is the temperature field, $K(\mathbf{r})$ is the thermal conductivity and ∇ represents partial differentiation. Equation 1 is accompanied with appropriate initial conditions and boundary conditions such as

$$\begin{aligned} T(\mathbf{r}, t) &= T^o(\mathbf{r}) && \text{on the boundary} \\ T(\mathbf{r}, 0) &= f(\mathbf{r}) && \text{at } t = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The space varying nature of $K(r)$ characterizes the FGM. The corresponding eigenvalue problem for Eqn 1 is

$$\nabla \cdot (K(\mathbf{r}) \nabla \phi_\alpha(\mathbf{r})) + \lambda_\alpha \phi_\alpha(\mathbf{r}) = 0, \quad (3)$$

where $\phi_\alpha(\mathbf{r})$ and λ_α are the α -th eigenfunction and eigenvalue, respectively [3]. It is noted that the eigenfunctions are mutually orthogonal and can be normalized as

$$(\phi_\alpha, \phi_\beta) = \delta_{\alpha\beta}, \quad (4)$$

where (f, g) denotes the inner product defined as

$$(f, g) \equiv \int_{\Omega} f(\mathbf{r})g(\mathbf{r})d\mathbf{r}, \quad (5)$$

and $\delta_{\alpha\beta}$ is the Kronecker delta. The symbol Ω in Eqn 5 denotes the entire material points.

The standard solution procedure for the Sturm-Liouville system of Eqn 3 can be used to express the temperature field, $T(\mathbf{r}, t)$, by a series of eigenfunctions. According to this method, the temperature field, $T(\mathbf{r}, t)$, can be expanded by the eigenfunctions of Eqn 3 with unknown coefficients, $c_\alpha(t)$, as

$$T(\mathbf{r}, t) = \sum_{\alpha=1}^{\infty} c_{\alpha}(t)\phi_{\alpha}(x). \quad (6)$$

By substituting Eqn 6 into Eqn 1, one deduces

$$\rho C_p \frac{dc_{\alpha}}{dt} = -\lambda_{\alpha} c_{\alpha}. \quad (7)$$

Equation 7 can be solved for $c_{\alpha}(t)$ as

$$c_{\alpha}(t) = A_{\alpha} e^{-\frac{\lambda_{\alpha}}{\rho C_p} t}. \quad (8)$$

The unknown coefficient, A_{α} , can be determined from the initial condition as

$$A_{\alpha} = (f(\mathbf{r}), \phi_{\alpha}(\mathbf{r})), \quad (9)$$

where $(,)$ denotes the inner product.

The α -th eigenfunction, $\phi_{\alpha}(\mathbf{r})$, can be approximated by using the Galerkin method in which the eigenfunction, $\phi_{\alpha}(\mathbf{r})$, is expanded by a series of admissible functions, $f^A(\mathbf{r})$, each of which satisfies the accompanying homogeneous boundary condition as

$$\phi_{\alpha}(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_A d_{\alpha}^A f^A(\mathbf{r}), \quad (10)$$

where d_{α}^A 's are unknown coefficients yet to be determined and $f^A(\mathbf{r})$'s are admissible functions chosen from a complete set of polynomial or transcendental functions that satisfy the homogeneous boundary condition. For example, if the boundary shape is 2-D circular, the admissible function can be chosen as $f(x, y) = (x^2 + y^2 - a^2)x^i y^j$ where a is the radius of the circle and i and j are ordered integers.

By substituting Eqn 10 into Eqn 3, multiplying by $f^B(\mathbf{r})$ on the both sides and integrating the result over the entire material domain, the eigenvalue problem of Eqn 3 in partial differential equation format is converted into an algebraic eigenvalue problem as

$$A\mathbf{d} + \lambda B\mathbf{d} = 0, \quad (11)$$

where

$$A_{AB} = \int_{\Omega} \nabla \cdot (K(\mathbf{r})\nabla f^A(\mathbf{r})) f^B(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r}, \quad (12)$$

and

$$B_{AB} = \int_{\Omega} f^A(\mathbf{r}) f^B(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r}. \quad (13)$$

The components of Eqns 12-13 can be evaluated using a computer algebra system. Thus, the transient temperature field can be obtained semi-analytically.

THERMAL STRESS ANALYSIS

With the known temperature distribution in an FGM, the displacement equilibrium equation in the FGM is expressed as

$$(C_{ijkl}(\mathbf{r})u_{k,l})_j - (C_{ijkl}(\mathbf{r})\alpha_{kl}(\mathbf{r})\delta T(\mathbf{r}))_{,j} = 0, \quad (14)$$

with the prescribed boundary condition where $C_{ijkl}(\mathbf{r})$, $u_k(\mathbf{r})$, $\alpha_{kl}(\mathbf{r})$ and $\delta T(\mathbf{r})$ are the elastic modulus, displacement, thermal expansion coefficient and temperature rise, respectively. Partial differentiation with respect to x_j is represented by $_{,j}$. The summation convention is used where applicable. The displacement field, $u_k(\mathbf{r})$, can be expressed as [4]

$$u_k(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_A c^A \psi_k^A(\mathbf{r}), \quad (15)$$

$$c^A = \frac{\int_{\Omega} b_i(\mathbf{r}) \psi_i^A(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r}}{\lambda^A}, \quad (16)$$

where for shortness, $b_i(\mathbf{r})$ represents the second term on the left hand side of Eqn 14 and $\psi_i^A(\mathbf{r})$ and λ_i^A are the A -th eigenfunction and eigenvalue, respectively, defined for the following eigenvalue problem similar to Eqn 3 as

$$(C_{ijkl}(\mathbf{r}) \psi_{k,l}^A(\mathbf{r}))_{,j} + \lambda^A \psi_i^A(\mathbf{r}) = 0, \quad (17)$$

where no summation is taken over A and the eigenfunction, $\psi_k^A(\mathbf{r})$ must satisfy the homogeneous boundary condition.

The eigenfunctions are mutually orthonormal as

$$\int_{\Omega} \psi_i^A(\mathbf{r}) \psi_i^B(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r} = \delta_{AB}. \quad (18)$$

Similar to the development of transient heat conduction, the eigenfunction, $\psi_i^A(\mathbf{r})$, can be approximated using the Galerkin method in which the eigenfunction, $\psi_i^A(\mathbf{r})$, is expanded by a series of admissible functions, $f^\beta(\mathbf{r})$, each of which satisfies the accompanying homogeneous boundary condition as

$$\psi_k^A(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{\beta} c_k^{A\beta} f^\beta(\mathbf{r}), \quad (19)$$

where $c_k^{A\beta}$ are unknown coefficients to be determined and $f^\beta(\mathbf{r})$'s are admissible functions. By substituting Eqn 19 into Eqn 17, multiplying by $f^\gamma(\mathbf{r})$ on both sides and integrating over the entire material domain, the eigenvalue problem of equation Eqn 17 in partial differential equation form is converted into an algebraic eigenvalue problem as

$$A\mathbf{c} + \lambda B\mathbf{c} = 0, \quad (20)$$

where

$$A_{ik}^{\beta\gamma} = \int_{\Omega} (C_{ijkl}(\mathbf{r}) f_{l}^{\beta}(\mathbf{r}))_{,j} f^{\gamma}(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r}, \quad (21)$$

and

$$B^{\beta\gamma} = \int_{\Omega} f^{\beta}(\mathbf{r}) f^{\gamma}(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r}. \quad (22)$$

For 2-D, Eqn 20 can be written as

$$\begin{pmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_1^A \\ c_2^A \end{pmatrix} + \lambda^A \begin{pmatrix} B & 0 \\ 0 & B \end{pmatrix} = 0, \quad (23)$$

where each component of Eqn 23 is a matrix or vector. The components of Eqns 21-22 can be evaluated exactly using a computer algebra system.

It is noted that the Green's function for the FGM can be constructed from the eigenfunctions as [5]

$$g_{km}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') = \sum_A \frac{\psi_m^A(\mathbf{r})\psi_k^A(\mathbf{r}')}{\lambda^A}, \quad (24)$$

where $g_{km}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ is defined as

$$(C_{ijkl}(\mathbf{r})g_{km}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'), l)_j + \delta_{im}\delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}') = 0, \quad (25)$$

with the homogeneous boundary condition and $\delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}')$ is the Dirac delta function. If the boundary condition is given by other than the Dirichlet condition, the admissible functions need to be modified accordingly. It is noted that the use of computer algebra system is essential in evaluating $A_{ik}^{\beta\gamma}$ and $B^{\beta\gamma}$ [2].

EXAMPLES AND CONCLUSIONS

In the absence of available experimental data to be compared with the present approach, a virtual FGM needs to be made up and numerical examples are presented in this section. Figure 1 is an example of the transient temperature field profiles, $T(\mathbf{r}, t)$, in a rectangular isotropic body defined over $\{(x, y), 0 < x < 1, 0 < y < 1\}$ subject to the Dirichlet type homogeneous boundary condition on the boundary computed at $t = 0.001$ and $t = 0.005$ (non-dimensionalized). The boundary temperature is homogeneous and the initial temperature of $T = 1$ is assumed. The thermal conductivity ($K(\mathbf{r})$) is assumed to vary in the form of $K^0 + K^1x + K^2y$ although this choice is rather arbitrary.

Figure 1: Temperature distributions ($t = 0.001$ and $t = 0.005$).

Figure 2 is an example of (non-dimensionalized) thermal stresses (von Mises' stress) under steady-state heat conduction in the same rectangular body as in Figure 1 subject to the Dirichlet type homogeneous boundary condition ($T = 0$ and $u_i = 0$) on the boundary and the same temperature initial and boundary conditions as in Figure 1. The elastic modulus ($C_{ijkl}(\mathbf{r})$) and the thermal expansion coefficients are assumed to vary in the form of $C_{ijkl}^0 + C_{ijkl}^1x + C_{ijkl}^2y$. For the purpose of illustrations, the values of all the material properties are taken to be unity.

The practical difficulties with the above approach are (A) determination of trial functions, $f^\alpha(\mathbf{r})$ and (B) computation of the A and B matrices in Eqns 12-13 or Eqns 21-22. If the region is expressed by a set of curved lines ($f_1(x, y) = 0, f_2(x, y) = 0 \dots$), the trial function for Dirichlet boundary conditions (the displacement, u_i , is given) can be expressed as

Figure 2: Von Mises stress distribution (at $t = 0.001$ and $t = 0.005$).

$f^\alpha(x, y) = f_1(x, y) \times f_2(x, y) \times \dots \times x^{\alpha_i} y^{\beta_j}$ where α_i and β_j are ordered integers. A computer algebra system can be used to expand the integrands in Eqns 12-13 or Eqns 21-22. The integrands are expressed in the form of $\sum \sum b_{ij} x^i y^j$ so that integration of Eqns 12-13 or Eqns 21-22 over the given region is reduced to integration of $x^i y^j$ which can be carried out analytically for a wide variety of shapes. The proposed method has a potential of being used to aide designing optimum material distribution in FGMs.

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